

Development of Ice Hockey Sticks using Braided Composites

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SUMMARY

In this study, ice hockey sticks were fabricated by using braiding technique. The relationships between the braiding angle and mechanical properties of rectangular braided sticks were investigated by three-point bending test. Finally, braiding technology can realize the ice hockey sticks which have various mechanical properties and safety.

*Keywords: ice hockey stick, microscopic observation,
mechanical property, braiding technology*

INTRODUCTION

The fiber reinforced plastic material is widely used as industrial materials instead of steel materials because of its superior specific strength. However, conventional composite laminates have very poor strength through the thickness and this leads to a limitation of their applications in structural parts with complex shapes. In order to overcome the limitation, the three-dimensional reinforced composite structures have been studied¹⁻⁶, and recently, tubular composite material has been used as structural material such as sporting goods, platform of vehicle, construction products and so on. As often as not, composite tubular members are manufactured with sheet laminating with unidirectional prepreg sheet and filament winding methods. Using textile material as reinforcements for fabricating composite tube, plain woven fabric or tubular braided fabric are often used. Woven fabric and tubular braided fabric have similar structure in microscopic view, but braided fabric has good features as fiber assembly.

The schematic drawing of braided fabric is shown in Fig. 1. In the braided fabric, the all fiber bundles are continuously oriented, so excellent mechanical properties of the composite materials with the braided fabric have been expected. Moreover, fiber bundles called braiding fiber are diagonally oriented, and the orientation angle of braiding fiber to the longitudinal direction can be adjusted freely. The orientation angle is defined as "Braiding angle". Also, the fiber bundle called "Middle-end fiber" (MEF) can be inserted between braiding fiber in longitudinal direction. Therefore the mechanical properties of the braided composite materials can be variously designed according to the requirements. In addition, by using the braiding technique, braided fabrics with various cross sectional shape can be fabricated such as rectangular and H shapes etc. For these reasons mentioned above, braided composite is suitable for customized sporting goods.

As structural members, tubular and rectangular pipes are essential configuration and widely used in various industrial fields. Heretofore, the study of a design methodology for a tubular composite pipe with braided fabric etc. has been studied⁷⁻¹⁰, but there are a few studies for the rectangular composite pipes. There are problems of rectangular pipes; the stress concentration is generated at the corners because rectangular pipes have corners and a curvature, and the deformation of the rectangular pipe is different from the one of the cylinder pipe. It is considered that the deformation of the hollow rectangular pipe is very complicated.

In this study, ice hockey sticks were fabricated by using braiding technique. The relationships between the braiding angle and mechanical properties of rectangular braided sticks were investigated by three-point bending test. Additionally, in order to clarify the fracture behavior of the braided tube, the fracture aspects of the ice hockey sticks and the braided tube were observed.

Fig. 1 Schematic drawing of braided fabric.

THREE-POINT BENDING TEST

Fabrication

The specifications of each specimen are shown in Table 1. Four kinds of the braided rectangular pipes with different braiding angle were fabricated in this study. The braided rectangular pipes with 30, 40, 50 and 60 degree braiding angle were called BA30, BA40, BA50 and BA60. These braided pipes were fabricated by tubular braiding machine (Murata Machinery, Ltd.) using 48 carbon prepreg yarns (UT500-12-RC38-SX3: TOHO TENAX Co., Ltd.) as the braiding fiber. The braided rectangular pipe of 60 degree braiding angle with MEF called BAM60 was fabricated by using 48 yarns as the braiding fiber and 12 yarns as MEF. In the case of braided fabric, the thickness of a layer with different braiding angle is different. Also, the thickness is increased by inserting MEF. Therefore, the number of layers was changed to keep almost the same thickness of composite. BA30, BA40 and BA50 had two braided layers, and BA60 and BAM60 had one braided layer.

For the fabrication process, prepreg yarns were braided around the rectangular shaped mandrel with 26.0 mm in width and 16.0 mm in height. Each specimen was about 28.0 mm in width, 18.0 mm in height and 1.00 mm in thickness.

Table 1 Specifications of each specimen

Specimen	Braiding angle (degree)	Braiding fiber	Middle-end fiber	Number of layer	Thickness (mm)
BA30	30	48	0	2	1.05
BA40	40			2	1.12
BA50	50			2	1.32
BA60	60			1	0.895
BAM60	60			12	1

Experiments

The three-point bending test was performed by using the aluminum solid-core bar as shown in Fig. 2. The aluminum solid-core bars are capable of decreasing the stress concentration generating at the point of support and loading nose. The bending modulus was examined both by deflection of cross-head and the strain obtained by strain gauge. The strain gauge was attached at the center and bottom part of the rectangular pipe. The bending test was performed by using an INSTRON universal testing machine (Type4206) with a span length of 150 mm and cross-head speed of 1.0 mm/min.

Fig. 2 Schematic drawing of three-point bending test.

Results and Discussion

Stress-Deflection curves of each specimen are shown in Fig. 3. Table 2 shows two kinds of experimental moduli calculated from the deflection, and the strain from strain gauge, the theoretical moduli in longitudinal direction and the bending strengths of each specimen. The theoretical moduli of each specimen were calculated by lamination theory assuming braided composites with braiding angle θ as unidirectional sheet laminates with fiber orientation angle $[+\theta/-\theta]$. The number of MEF of BAM60 was decided by assuming that the theoretical modulus of BAM60 was corresponding to that of BA40.

In BA30, BA40, BA50 and BA60, it was found that both bending moduli and bending strength were decreased with an increase in the braiding angle. Also, bending modulus of BAM60 were the almost same as that of BA40. The trend of the bending moduli of each specimen with the deflection and with the strain was the same as the

theoretical modulus of each specimen in longitudinal direction, and one with deflection were lower than one with strain for all specimens. The difference between both moduli became smaller with increase in the braiding angle. The bending strengths were decreased with an increase in the braiding angle.

Fig. 3 Stress-Deflection curves of each specimen.

Table 2 Bending moduli and bending strengths of each specimen.

Specimen	Bending modulus calculated by deflection (GPa)	Bending modulus calculated by strain (GPa)	Theoretical modulus in longitudinal direction (GPa)	Bending strength (MPa)
BA30	17.7	38.6	46.0	201.3
BA40	12.7	15.5	23.0	180.1
BA50	8.36	10.9	13.4	144.2
BA60	7.15	7.50	9.6	78.65
BAM60	10.6	14.0	23.3	138.0

ICE HOCKEY STICKS

Fracture behaviour of ice hockey sticks

The photograph of actual ice hockey sticks after the accident was shown in Fig. 4. In the shaft A, the fracture occurred at more anterior position than the standard position of the hands. It was considered that the fracture of the shaft A was caused by the damage of the impact with the packs. In the shaft B, the fracture occurred at near the standard position of hands. It was considered that the fracture of the shaft B was caused by the cumulative load from the hands. In the shaft C, the fracture occurred between both hands.

In common of each shaft, many delaminations between each fiber sheet were observed. The typical fracture aspects of ice hockey stick after the accident was shown in Fig. 5. The stick was split down into two with many delamination. In this way, it was found that the shafts had some fracture behavior in the different place of a shaft.

The players believe that the fracture was caused by same impact load to the shaft from the pack and so on. The initiation point should be identified in order to understand the fracture, prevent the fracture, and create a new safely stick.

According to microscopic observation on fracture surface not only some cracks but also voids, fiber discontinuity and some defects which occur during the fabrication could be seen. Therefore careful fabrication system should be established. However by using unidirectional aligned composites their fracture behavior was very sensitive to the defects, even if the defect size was small. One of the solutions for presentation of stick fracture should be changing reinforcement configuration from unidirectional composites to other aspects.

Here, we proposed braided fabric. Their fracture behavior is not so brittle due to weaving states than unidirectional composites.

Fig. 4 Photograph of ice hockey stick after the accident

Fig. 5 Fracture aspects of ice hockey stick after the accident

Braiding shaft

At the accident in playing ice hockey the shafts often are broken down into the two pieces. Sometimes the broken stick would cause additional accident during the game. Therefore one of the concepts of safety shaft in which the fracture can be permitted but disconnected fracture cannot be allowed. According to this concept the experimental results of braided composite tubes which were subjected by impact bending load were shown.

The list of braided tubes was shown in Table 3. N45, N45A and N45B had 60 degrees (1st layer) and 45 degrees (after 2nd layer) braiding angle, and N3045AL had 60 degrees (1st layer), 30 degrees (2nd layer) and 45 degrees (after 3rd layer) braiding angle. They have 4 or 5 layers in the case of N45, N45A and N45B, and the position of MEF is different; in N45, MEF with 6000 filament numbers was inserted into all layers. In N45A, MEF with 12000 filament numbers were inserted into 2nd and 3rd layers, whereas in N45B MEF was inserted into 4th and 5th layers. In N3045AL, MEF with 24000 filament numbers were inserted into the 2nd layer.

The fracture aspects of the braided tubes after impact bending tests were shown in Fig. 6. N45, M45A and N45B broke down and were divided in half. In N3045AL, there was no disconnected fracture and two pieces were connected by MEF.

The absorbed energies of the tubes were shown in Fig. 7. Here, the absorbed energy of N45 was based. The absorbed energy of N45A increased 40% and the one of N45B increased 10% from the N45. Particularly, N3045AL with disconnected fracture showed the highest value which was almost twice of N45. It was considered that MEF resided at inner side and had large filament numbers was good.

Therefore braiding technology can realize the ice hockey shaft which has various mechanical properties and safety.

Table 3 The list of braided tubes

Specimen type		N45	N45A	N45B	N3045AL	
Number of braid layer		5	5	5	4	
Braid pattern*	Layer	MEF/BF	MEF/BF	MEF/BF	MEF/BF	
	inner	1st	0_0k/60_3k	0_0k/60_3k	0_0k/60_3k	0_0k/60_3k
		2nd	0_6k/45_3k	0_12k/45_3k	0_0k/45_3k	0_24k/30_3k
		3rd	0_6k/45_3k	0_12k/45_3k	0_0k/45_3k	0_0k/45_3k
		4th	0_6k/45_3k	0_0k/45_3k	0_12k/45_3k	0_0k/45_3k
	outer	5th	0_6k/45_3k	0_0k/45_3k	0_12k/45_3k	
Percent 0°yams	(%)	34.4	34.4	34.4	40.1	
Materials	Fiber	Carbon	Carbon	Carbon	Carbon	
	Resin	Epoxy	Epoxy	Epoxy	Epoxy	
Inner diameter	(mm)	21.0	21.0	21.0	21.0	
Outer diameter	(mm)	24.6	24.5	24.6	23.8	
Bending modulus	(GPa)	41.9	40.9	42.1	53.8	

Fig. 6 The fracture aspects of braided tubes after impact bending tests

Fig. 7 The absorbed energy of the tubes

CONCLUSION

In this study, in order to entertain the availability of the braided structure for ice hockey sticks, three-point bending test was performed, and microscopic observation was performed for the braided structure after impact bending test.

From the results of three-point bending test, it was found that the bending moduli and the bending strengths of each specimen were decreased with an increase in the braiding angle. From the results of microscopic observation after impact bending test, the specimen broke down and was divided in half when the middle-end fiber with 12000 filament numbers was inserted into inter or outer layer. However, when the middle-end fiber with 24000 filament numbers was inserted into inter layer, there was no disconnected fracture and two pieces were connected by the middle-end fiber. Particularly, the braided tube which the middle-end fiber with 24000 filament numbers was inserted into inter layer showed the highest value which was almost twice of the one which the middle-end fiber 6000 filament numbers was inserted.

Therefore braiding technology can realize the ice hockey shaft which has various mechanical properties and safety shaft.

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